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Dear Elham Mousavian and Claudia Casapulla,

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Automated Shape Adjustment of Interlocking Joints for Structurally Informed Design of Masonry Block Assemblages

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Abstract. This paper introduces a tool to design structurally informed assemblages of interlocking blocks. First, the static problem of limit analysis is extended to assemblages with openings and a running bond pattern. Then, a method to measure the assemblage infeasibility due to the sliding resistance violation (namely sliding infeasibility) is described. An optimization procedure is finally presented to minimise the measured sliding infeasibility by automatically changing the shape of interlocking joints.

1. Introduction

The mechanical improvement of block assemblages through finding the best interlocking joint shapes has recently been of significant interest to the fields of architecture and structural engineering. Several studies have addressed the relation between different joint shapes and the assembly's structural performances [1-3], though mostly investigating the influence of limited geometric parameters of modular interlocking blocks on the wall in-plane or out-of-plane behaviours. Few methods have been developed to design structurally wise shapes for dry interlocking joints: Yao et al. [4] have developed a tool that first provides the user with an interface to design the desired joints between the rigid parts, then analyse the stability of the model and suggest how to remove the instability; Rippmann [5] has shown that the bearing capacity of a compression-only, rigid, and frictionless body does not change after being partitioned by non-planar (interlocking) joints normal to the flow of axial forces. The authors of this paper have developed a tool within the European SiDMACIB Project, No. 791235 MCSA_IF, as one of the first efforts to design structurally sound masonry assemblages of interlocking blocks with finite shear and friction. The SiDMACIB tool is based on a two-step procedure: it first extends the static problem of limit analysis to orthotropic corrugated joints [6], and then quantifies the structural infeasibility due to the violation of the sliding resistance, namely "sliding infeasibility measure" (SIM) [7]. The standard and non-standard limit analysis [8-10] is a powerful method to analyse masonry structures with more computational efficiency when compared to other well-known methods including finite element [11] and discrete element [12] analyses. On the other hand, the concept of measuring how far a model is from being structurally feasible has firstly been introduced by Whiting et al. [13] and it is a powerful tool to minimize the structural infeasibility by automatically or manually adjusting the initial shape or material parameters assigned by the user. This paper presents an optimization method which automatically tunes the interlocking joint shapes to minimize the SIM, i.e., to remove the structural infeasibility of the initial model. The optimization particularly changes the orientation of the locks at the interlocking joints to minimize the sliding infeasibility.

2.1. validation

The static problem has been implemented to develop a grasshopper plugin, using C#, while the MATLAB's lsqin has been used to solve the linear equilibrium equation. The benchmark problem chosen for validating the implemented static problem is a vertical wall with the running bond pattern and one opening, subjected to in-plane loading. The chosen wall is in fact the third benchmark wall problem provided by Gilbert et al. [10] (figure 1). It is composed of blocks with 4×1.75 units of length subjected to one unit of vertical force (block weight) and one unit of lateral force. Also, the friction coefficient is considered 0.65. The collapse load factors λ for associative friction reported in [10] and this paper are 0.40369 and 0.40368, respectively, and this good matching can validate the implemented method.

3. SIM optimization

This section briefly introduces the method to quantify the sliding infeasibility of interlocking assemblages (sliding infeasibility measure SIM). The method was elaborated in detail in [7]. To measure the sliding infeasibility, the sliding constraints can be removed from Equation (1) so that the internal forces can take any value. For each contact point, the absolute value of the tangential force violating the sliding valid ranges can then be considered as the local SIM. Summing (functions of) the local SIMs at all contact points, the overall SIM of the assemblage can be calculated. For an infeasible assemblage, equation (1) with the removed sliding constraints may find several solutions, i.e., several SIM might exist. To find the solution with the lowest SIM, equation (1) can be reformulated as follows. First, the tangential force at each contact point r^t is decomposed into two new variables r^{ta} and r^{tb} , where $r^{ta} + r^{tb} = r^t$; while r^{ta} has to satisfy the sliding constraints, r^{tb} can take any value and therefore r^t can also take any value. Then, an optimization problem is formulated which tries to minimize r^{tb} , making r^t as close as possible to r^{ta} (within the sliding valid range), while the assemblage is constrained as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \text{Objective function} \\ \text{Equilibrium equation} \\ \text{compression constraint} \\ \text{friction constraint} \\ \text{shear constraint} \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{cases} \text{SIM}_\theta = \min \sum_{\eta=1}^L [(r_\eta^{pj,t1b})^2 + (r_\eta^{pj,t2b})^2] \\ \text{subjected to:} & C_{eq,\theta} \cdot \vec{r} + \vec{E} = 0 \\ & \vec{r}^{pj,\vec{n}} \leq 0 \\ & |\vec{r}^{pj,t1a}| \leq \mu |\vec{r}^{pj,\vec{n}}| \\ & |\vec{r}^{pj,t2a}| \leq 0.33 T_0 \end{cases}$$

where $r_\eta^{pj,t1b}$ and $r_\eta^{pj,t2b}$ are the tangential forces parallel and normal to the lock at the generic contact point η , respectively, L is the total number of contact points, \vec{r} is the vector of variables containing the internal forces r^{t1a} , r^{t1b} , r^{t2a} , r^{t2b} , and r^n at all the contact points. The designer can adjust θ manually to minimize the SIM and remove the sliding infeasibility of an assemblage of interlocking blocks, which is in fact the result of the objective function at the optimal solution.

4. Lock-orientation optimization

This section introduces the lock-orientation optimization algorithm by which the initial lock orientations assigned by the user are automatically tuned to minimize the SIM. Before elaborating this optimization, first the concept of function in programming is introduced. In computer programming, a function is a black box containing a block of codes getting a number of inputs, executing several tasks and returning outputs. This black box can then be called again so that its output is a function of the selected inputs. To develop the lock-orientation optimization, a function is defined to compute the SIM and its name is simply "SIA" standing for sliding feasibility analyser. The SIA inputs are a set of lock orientations $\theta = \{\theta_{uv0}, \theta_{uv1}, \theta_{uw}, \theta_{vw}\}$ and another set, called "assigned_inputs", including all the parameters assigned by the designer, such as the lock numbers ($N = \{N_{uv0}, N_{uv1}, N_{uw}, N_{vw}\}$), coordinates of the block corners, external loads and moments, indices of the block faces acting as supports, and material properties μ and τ_k . When a lock number in set N is assigned zero, the related faces are considered to be flat and therefore, the related lock orientation does not change the SIM

value. Using MATLAB, SIA can be written as shown in figure 2.

```
function SIM = SIA (theta, assigned_inputs)
%% C_ineq,RHS_ineq,C_eq,E construction
%% C_obj construction
%% r0 construction
%% Optimization
    f = @(r) C_obj* r.^2; %objective function
    [r,SIM] = fmincon(f,r0,C_ineq,RHS_ineq,C_eq,E); %optimization
end
```

Figure 2. MATLAB code snippet for SIA function

This function first constructs the matrices and vectors of equation (2), including: the coefficient matrix “c_eq” and the right-hand side vector “E” of the equality constraint (equilibrium equation in equation (2)); the coefficient matrix “c_ineq” and right-hand side vector “RHS_ineq” of the inequality constraint (normal and sliding constraints of equation (2)); the coefficient vector “c_obj” multiplied by optimization variables “r” to the power 2 to define the equation (2) objective function; and the initial value of the variables “r0”. How they are constructed is folded (hidden) in the code snippet. Then, the optimization objective function “f”, whose variables are the internal forces “r”, is defined using the syntax “@r” and the MATLAB’s fmincon solves this quadratic function. Finally, the SIM that is the value of the f at the optimal solution is returned as the SIA output and the SIM can be called again as a function of θ : $SIM = @(theta) SIA (theta, assigned_inputs)$. The next step is to define another black box function which gets the inputs assigned by the user in a grasshopper component (through C#) and returns the optimal θ . It is named LOO, standing for the lock-orientation optimizer (figure 3).

```
function theta = LOO (assigned_inputs)
SIM = @(theta) SIA (theta, assigned_inputs); %objective function
theta0 = [0,0,0,0]; %initial theta
lb(1:4)=0; %theta lower bound
ub(1:4)=pi; %theta upper bound
theta = fmincon(SIM,theta0,[],[],[],[],lb,ub); %optimization
end
```

Figure 3. MATLAB code snippet for LOO function

This function sets up all the necessary materials for the lock orientation optimization, i.e.: a set of initial values for θ from which the optimization starts (θ_{theta0}); the objective function SIM whose variable is theta; and the upper “ub” and lower “lb” bounds for θ which are zero and π . LOO inputs are the “assigned_inputs” introduced above, including all the shape and material properties needed to find the SIM. LOO gets the assigned_inputs from the grasshopper component and passes on them to the SIA function that is invoked in LOO. MATLAB’s fmincon is used to solve the shape optimization. Finally, the optimal θ (i.e., the optimal θ_{uv0} , θ_{uv1} , θ_{uw} , and θ_{vw}) is returned as the LOO output.

4.1.1. Validation

To validate the shape optimization, a simple setup of two blocks is considered, where the lower block is fully fixed and the upper one is subjected to a lateral force. This setup was previously addressed in [6] to study the torsion-shear resistance of interlocking blocks. The setup dimensions and the forces applied to the block centroids are shown in figure 4. The shear strength and the friction coefficient are 0.25 N/m² and 0, respectively. In this model, only the vw faces are considered to be interlocking. The lateral force imposed to the upper block is the collapse load for the case in which the two considered locks are normal to the force.

First, the SIM is obtained manually by solving equation (2) for different values of θ_{vw} changed by the user. As shown in figure 4, when the locks are parallel to the lateral force the system is infeasible since the frictional resistance is zero and cannot avoid sliding at the interface. The largest SIM is recorded for this case (7.45 N²). Changing θ_{vw} , the sliding resistance is increased since both joint shear and frictional resistances are involved in the sliding prevention. For $\theta_{vw} = 1.57$ rad, the SIM is 2.2×10^{-4} , meaning that the sliding infeasibility is removed when the locks are normal to the lateral

force. In the second step, the lock-orientation optimization is executed to the same setup, setting the lock orientation initial values as $\theta^0 = \{0, 0, 0, 0\}$, i.e., the optimization starts from the case in which the two locks are parallel to the lateral force, causing the largest SIM. The assigned lock numbers are $N = \{0, 0, 0, 2\}$, which means that only the vw faces are interlocking with two locks. As a result, only the initial value of θ_{vw} will be changed during the optimization. The optimal θ_{vw} found by the shape optimization is 1.566477 rad and its corresponding SIM is 3.2×10^{-4} which is very close to the minimum SIM found manually (2.2×10^{-4}).

Figure 4. Left: The validation setup (the black points are the supports). Right: Relation between the SIM and lock orientation found manually

5. Conclusions

This paper demonstrated and validated an extension of the static problem of limit analysis to assemblages of interlocking blocks with the running bond pattern and openings. A method was proposed to measure the assemblage sliding infeasibility and a shape optimization was developed to automatically adjust the lock orientations to minimise the measured infeasibility. The optimization was validated by comparing the SIMs for different lock orientations obtained manually and the minimum SIM automatically found by the optimization.

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